

Synthesis and Dissociation Constants of some Aromatic Hydroxamic Acids

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Synthetic procedures for several hydroxamic acids are described. Acid dissociation constants of these ligand acids have been determined by the usual pH titration technique. A discussion on the variation of the acid dissociation constants with the nature of the substituent group in the aromatic ring has been made.

In connection with our studies on the vanadium(V) complexes of aromatic hydroxamic acids there arose the need for synthesis of a large number of hydroxamic acid and of evaluating their acid dissociation constants. In order to obtain readily a number of these hydroxamic acids, we tried to utilise the simplest possible route. The method involving the preparation of the cupric salts of the hydroxamic acids, followed by decomposition of the complex with H_2S was not found to be quite suitable. The method followed by Wise and Brandt¹ was to run the methanol solution of the potassium salt of the hydroxamic acid through a H^+ form cation exchanger and finally to recover the acids after removal of the solvent. These authors have found the Blatt's procedure² suitable only for benzo-hydroxamic acid.

We have used the Blatt procedure in most cases with advantage after some slight modifications.

All these hydroxamic acids were found to give rise to violet colour or red precipitate with $Fe(III)$ in suitable pH, to a violet-black precipitate with vanadium(V) at aqueous medium around pH 3, which turned red in presence of alcohols. These reactions are characteristic for hydroxamic acids.

Acid dissociation constants of some hydroxamic acids were determined by Wise and Brandt¹ by measuring the pH of a solution containing known amounts of the free acid and its sodium salt. Electrical conductance was also used to evaluate the K_a of the hydroxamic acids. Acid dissociation constants of benzo-hydroxamic acid has been determined potentiometrically as also spectrophotometrically by two groups in recent time.³⁻⁴ Besides, acid dissociation constants of the salicylhydroxamic acid has also been reported⁵.

1. Wise and Brandt, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 2361.
2. Blatt, *Organic Synthesis*.
3. Barnocelli and Grossi, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1955, 27(5), 1087.
4. Allmarin et. al., *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1963, 18(3), 342-7.
5. Bhaduri and Ghosh, *Z. Anorg. U. allgem. Chemie*, 1958, 297, 73.

Dissociation constants of substituted benzoic acids depends on (1) the electronic effects of the substituent groups and (2) the steric effects of the substituents, when it is present in an ortho position with respect to the carboxylic acid group⁶. The major purpose of this study was to find out whether similar effects also prevailed in a series of substituted aromatic hydroxamic acids. Further, in this case of the substituted benzoic acids, the greater the acidity (the larger the K_a value) the greater is the ease of esterification provided the steric effect due to the substituent does not operate to any appreciable extent. Thus all the chlorobenzoic acids are more readily esterified than benzoic acid under identical conditions. In *O*-chlorobenzoic acid, the steric effect does prevail but the electronic effect due to an electron attracting Cl group outweighs the first effect. With *O*-fluorobenzoic acid, due to a lesser steric effect, the ease of esterification is even greater. Since this work arose directly out of our investigation of the complex $[VO(OH)(RH)_2]$ leading to $[VO(OAlK)(RH_2)]$,^{7,8,9} (RH_2 = a molecule of the aromatic hydroxamic acid) we determined the acid dissociation constants of the reagents in order to expose any relation between the acid dissociation constants of the ligands and the ease and difficulty of formation of the ester like complexes of vanadium(V).

Hydroxamic acids possess the reacting group $-\text{CONHOH}$, which may be viewed as $-\text{C} \begin{array}{l} \text{O}^{10,11} \\ \diagup \\ \text{NHOH} \end{array}$. The ligand benzohydroxamic acid (RR_2) may be considered to be dissociating as follows:—

(1) In near neutral or alkaline solution as :

(2) In acid solution depending on the tendency of the hydroxylamine nitrogen to get protonated, as :

In most cases, so far, the dissociation constants have been determined by potentiometric titration of the reagent acid without previous addition of extra acid to protonate the nitrogen.

6. Hammett, "Physical Organic Chemistry", p. 204, McGraw-Hill, New York (1940).
7. Dutta and Lahiri, *Jour. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 39, 860.
8. Dutta and Lahiri, *ibid.*, 1963, 40, 53.
9. Dutta and Ghosh, *ibid.*, under publication.
10. Usova and Voroshin, *Doklady Akad. Nauk. USSR*, 1957, 113, 1306.
11. Mathias, *Compt. rend.*, 1951, 232, 505.

We have titrated the hydroxamic acids by alkali in the presence of added acid (HCl) in 1M KNO_3 and evaluated the values of η (average number of hydrogen bound per hydroxamic acid group). The acid dissociation constants have been finally evaluated graphically from the knowledge of the pH corresponding to $\eta = 0.5$ (giving pK_1) and to $\eta = 1.5$ (giving pK_2). One sample titration data for O-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid is given in Table I. The Table II represents the two acid dissociation constants of the ten hydroxamic acids that have been studied potentiometrically. Our value of benzohydroxamic acid and a few other compares well with those reported earlier by other workers. The graphically obtained pK_1 values also agreed well with the pH of the half neutralisation point of the free reagent acid alone.

TABLE I
O-Nitro benzohydroxamic Acid.

Concentration of O-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid = 0.0025 M
= C
 $\text{KNO}_3 = 1\text{M}$. NaOH solution used = 1M

HCl added (in moles)	Alkali added (in moles)	Total acid before equilibrium C (in moles)	pH after equilibrium	(H^+) after equilibrium C_{H^+} (in moles)	Acid bound $\text{C}_0 - \text{C}_{\text{H}^+}$ (in moles)	$\eta = \frac{\text{C}_0 - \text{C}_{\text{H}^+}}{\text{C}_A}$
0.025	0	0.0275	1.62	0.02399	0.00351	1.04
"	0.65×10^{-2}	0.210	1.75	0.01778	0.00320	1.28
"	1.05 "	0.017	1.86	0.01380	0.00300	1.20
"	1.45 "	0.013	2.0	0.01000	0.00269	1.08
"	1.85 "	0.009	2.2	0.00631	0.00245	0.98
"	2.05 "	0.007	2.33	0.00467	0.00232	0.92
"	2.15 "	0.006	2.40	0.00395	0.00202	0.81
"	2.55 "	0.002	5.65		0.0020	0.80
"	2.60 "	0.0015	6.70		0.0015	0.60
"	2.65 "	0.0010	7.30		0.0010	0.40
"	2.70 "	0.0005	7.60		0.0005	0.20

Table II clearly indicates that the order of variation of the dissociation constants of the substituted benzohydroxamic acid parallels that of the corresponding substituted benzoic acids. Again, the way the acid dissociation constants has been found to vary in this series of co-ordinating ligands, brings the cases of recently studied N-substituted acetoacetamides and substituted salicylaldoximes for a rightful comparison. In the series of N-substituted acetoacetamides¹², the acid dissociation constants follows the order acetoacetanilide < 2-methoxy acetoacetanilide < 2-methyl acetoacetanilide < 2-chloroacetoacetanilide, the

TABLE II

Acid dissociation constants of substituted benzohydroxamic acids and benzoic acids.

Substituted Hydroxamic acids	This study		pK_{a1}	Substituted benzoic acids	pK^{13}
	pK_{a1}	pK_{a2}			
<i>O</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CONHOH	1.45	7.05		<i>O</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ COOH	2.17
<i>O</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ CONHOH	1.55	7.85		<i>O</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ COOH	2.94
<i>O</i> -FC ₆ H ₄ CONHOH	1.75	8.00		<i>O</i> -FC ₆ H ₄ COOH	3.26
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CONHOH	1.80	8.35		<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ COOH	3.42
<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CONHOH	1.85	8.40		<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ COOH	3.49
<i>O</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ CONHOH	1.87	8.55		<i>O</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ COOH	3.91
<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ CONHOH	1.90	8.62	8.585 (1)	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ COOH	3.98
C ₆ H ₅ CONHOH	1.85	8.805	8.97 + 0.03 (3) & 8.985 (1)	C ₆ H ₅ COOH	4.20
<i>p</i> -(OCH ₃)C ₆ H ₄ CONHOH	1.85	9.00	9.00 (1)	<i>p</i> -(OCH ₃)C ₆ H ₄ COOH	4.48

[¹ pK_{a1} denotes the values determined by other workers.]

[Figures in parentheses denote the reference number of the relevant study.]

substituents being present in the aromatic ring of the aniline entity. For 5-substituted salicylaldoxime¹³, the acid dissociation constants follows the order: 5-methyl salicylaldoxime < salicylaldoxime < 5-chlorosalicylaldoxime < 5-nitro salicylaldoxime. The substituted aromatic hydroxamic acids also follows almost the same sequence.

It is to be noted that, benzohydroxamic acid and other substituted aromatic hydroxamic acids having pK_a values lower than that of benzohydroxamic acid yield solid alkovo complexes with the exceptional cases of *m*-nitro and *o*-methyl benzohydroxamic acids.^{7,13,14} The case of *O*-methyl benzohydroxamic acid may

be explained by the fact that the effect of increase of K_a of *O*-methyl benzohydroxamic acid over benzohydroxamic acid due to hyperconjugation and consequent intramolecular hydrogen bonding between the carboxylate anion and a hydrogen

of the methyl group,^{14,15,16} having a nett effect of spreading the resultant negative charge, so as to stabilize the carboxylate anion, decreasing its capacity of recombination with the proton, is more than counteracted by the steric obstruction offered by the methyl group in the ortho position which resists the incoming of the alcohol molecule to form alkoxo derivative.

We would now like to examine the change in the dissociation constants (K_a) of the hydroxamic acids in a more quantitative manner. Of the nine hydroxamic acids reported in this paper only four are either meta or para substituted. The others being ortho substituted derivatives, are left out of our present consideration, as our immediate object is to examine how far our experimental data fits and Hammett equation. As is done by several workers^{6,17,18} in this field, we plotted the logarithm of the dissociation constants of the benzoic acids against those of the corresponding benzohydroxamic acids and obtained a straight line (Fig. 1). This linear log-log plot indicates that our benzohydroxamic acids

FIG. 1.

compare favourably with the corresponding benzoic acids. The Hammett equation for any reaction series is :

$$\log K - \log K_0 = \rho \sigma \quad \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

where K_0 = dissociation constant of the unsubstituted benzene derivative,
 K = dissociation constant of the substituted benzene derivative,

14. Baker and Nathan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1844.
15. W. A. Waters, "Physical Organic Chemistry" (Fifth edition), p. 70-71 and p. 264, Routledge & Kegan Paul Ltd. London.
16. Watson, "Modern Theories of Organic Chemistry", Oxford, 1937.
17. H. H. Jaffe, *Chem. Revs.*, 1953, 53, 191.
18. R. W. Taft, Jr. in M. S. Newman's "Steric Effects in Organic Chemistry", Ch. 13, John Wiley & Sons, Inc. N.Y. 1956.
19. L. P. Hammett, *Chem. Revs.*, 1935, 17, 125; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1938, 34, 156.

ρ is the substituent constant—a measure of the electron donating or electron withdrawing power of the substituent.

σ is the reaction constant and is a measure of the sensitivity of the equilibrium constant to the changes in the σ values of the substituents.

Following the procedure followed by Kindler^{19a} we proceeded to calculate out the quantity ρ for the dissociation of the hydroxamic acids in water at room temperature (21°C $\pm$ 1°C) with the help of the Hammett relationship and using the standard values²⁰ of σ and utilising our experimental values of K and K_0 . Considering the case of the *p*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid we have,

$$\begin{aligned}\log K &= -8.35 \\ \log K_0 &= -8.805 \\ \sigma &= +0.778^{20} \\ &\text{(for P-NO}_2\text{ group)}\end{aligned}$$

Substitution of these quantities in the equation at once lead to $\rho = 0.585^*$.

Using this value of ρ and utilising the standard values of σ for different substituents we now set out to examine whether our data fits the Hammett Equation or not. The results are given below.

Substituent	ρ^*	σ	$\log \frac{k}{k_0}$ Calculated	$\log \frac{k}{k_0}$ Experimentally Found
<i>m</i> -nitro	+ 0.585	+ 0.710	+ 0.415	+ 0.404
<i>p</i> -chloro	"	+ 0.222	+ 0.133	+ 0.185
<i>p</i> -methoxy	"	- 0.268	+ 0.157	- 0.195

The results indicate that the experimental and calculated results agree well in the case of *m*-nitro benzohydroxamic acid but show some deviation in the other two cases. This variation may be attributed to the fact that the σ values are not absolute constants because of the direct resonance interaction between the substituent group and the reaction centre, which is more effective in the case of *p*-substituted derivative than in the case of a meta compound. Elaborate study of this problem led several workers^{21, 22} to suggest alternative sets of constants. The substituent constants for para substituents capable of resonance electron withdrawal are called σ^- values and σ^+ values are for those substituents effecting resonance electron-donating para substituents. Furthermore, Van Bekkum, Verkade and

19a. K. Kindler, *Ann.*, 1926, 1, 450.

20. D. H. McDaniel and H. C. Brown, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, 23, 420.

21. R. W. Taft, Jr., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 1045.

22. H. C. Brown and Y. Okamoto, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 4979.

* calculated from the graph gives a value of 0.588.

Wepster²³ have described convincing evidence that not two but a multiplicity of a value would be required to correlate existing data in cases where there seems to be direct resonance between the substituent and the reaction centre which is the case with the hydroxamic acids studied here. An evidence in favour of the above argument may be cited now. The previously accepted values for σ and τ^- for the *p*-nitro substituent are + 0.778 and + 1.27 respectively. But it has been found out²⁴ that the calculated values of σ varied continuously from + 0.766 to + 1.378 in different reactions. Thus it will not be unreasonable to conclude that our experimental data regarding the dissociation constants of some of the meta and para substituted benzohydroxamic acids fairly obey the Hammett relationship and the reasons for the not too much deviation of the calculated value from the experimental data is evident from the above discussion.

The value of ρ in this series (+ 0.585) is much lower than that in the case of the benzoic acids which points out to the fact that the dissociation of the benzohydroxamic acids are less sensitive to the change in the substituent groups than in the cases of the corresponding benzoic acids and this is well corroborated by our experimental data given in Table.

EXPERIMENTAL

O-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid: Anhydrous hydroxylaminehydrochloride (8.0 g.) was dissolved in anhydrous methanol (40 mL) by refluxing on a steam bath. Potassium hydroxide (9.0 g.) was similarly dissolved in methanol (25 mL). The two solutions were cooled in ice and mixed well in stoppered flask and the precipitated KCl filtered off. Ethyl *O*-nitrobenzoate (8 g.) was then added to it and mixed well and the brownish liquid was kept overnight at room temperature. It was then concentrated by evaporation under a fan, cooled in freezing mixture and *O*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid was precipitated by the addition of dilute HCl until distinctly acid. It was filtered, washed with ice cold water and twice recrystallised from 0.5 N hot acetic acid. The final product is a white crystalline compound having a faint brownish tint. Found: N, 15.20%. Reqd. for $C_7H_6N_2O_4$: N, 15.38%.

p-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid: The same procedure as above is employed replacing ethyl *O*-nitrobenzoate by *p*-nitrobenzoate. The final product was obtained as colourless flakes. Found: N, 15.29%. Reqd. for $C_7H_6N_2O_4$: N, 15.38%.

m-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid: Obtained as above using methyl *m*-nitrobenzoate in place of ethyl *O*-nitrobenzoate, in white microcrystalline form. Found: N, 15.31%. Reqd. for $C_7H_6N_2O_4$: N, 15.38%.

23. H. Van Bekkum, P. E. Verkade and B. M. Wepster. *Rev. Trav. Chim.*, 1959, 78, 815
24. J. Hine, "Physical Organic Chemistry", (International students Edition, 1962) McGraw-Hill Book Co. Inc.

O-chlorobenzohydroxamic acid : The same procedure as in the case of *O*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid is employed, the ester used being the ethyl ester of *O*-chlorobenzoic acid, the concentration of the reaction mixture being effected on a steam bath. The final product obtained by recrystallising twice from hot water containing a little acetic acid, was in the form of small shiny flakes. Found : N, 8.06% Reqd. for $C_7H_6NO_2Cl$: N, 8.16%.

p-chlorobenzohydroxamic acid : In this case, the first portion of the method of preparation is same as above. After keeping overnight the liquid mixture containing alkali, hydroxylamine and ester deposited shiny flakes of the potassium salt, which was filtered, dissolved in water and some more alkali cooled in ice and reprecipitated by adding dilute HCl. It was then twice recrystallised from 0.5 N acetic acid. The final product was obtained as shiny flakes. Found : N, 8.08% Reqd. for $C_7H_6NO_2Cl$: N, 8.16%.

O-fluoro benzohydroxamic acid : Procedure same as in the case of the *O*-chloroanalogue. The precipitation of the free hydroxamic acid being done by the addition of acetic acid. Twice recrystallised product from 1N acetic acid was in the form of shiny white flakes. Found : N, 8.92% Reqd. for $C_7H_6NO_2F$: N, 9.03%.

p-methoxybenzohydroxamic acid : The procedure for *O*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid was adopted. Some potassium salt was precipitated on keeping overnight and filtered off and the filtrate was concentrated by evaporation under a fan, cooled in ice and the free hydroxamic acid was precipitated by adding dilute acetic acid. The final product (twice recrystallised from hot water containing a little acetic acid) was a white powdery substance having a faint pinkish tinge. Found : N, 8.30% Reqd. for $C_8H_8O_2N$: N, 8.38%.

Benzohydroxamic acid : Blatt's procedure was adopted here. The free hydroxamic acid was twice recrystallised from 1N acetic acid. Found : N, 10.17% Reqd. for $C_7H_7NO_2$: 10.22%.

O-methyl benzohydroxamic acid : Same procedure as in the case of benzohydroxamic acid. The recrystallised product was obtained in the form of small flakes. Found : N, 9.19% Reqd. for $C_8H_9NO_2$: N, 9.27%.

General Experimental Methods : Nitrogen was estimated by semimicro Dumas technique. The pH titration was done with the help of a Cambridge pH meter using a glass electrode of range 3-11 pH, the reference electrode being a calomel electrode. The standard alkali (1N) was added from a microburette to the hydroxamic acid solution (of 100 ml. volume 0.0025M with respect to the hydroxamic acid and 1N with respect to KNO_3) and the mixture stirred with the help of a magnetic stirrer. Titrations were done at $20^\circ \pm 1^\circ$.